

The Marketing Strategies of Live Streaming E-commerce Based on the SICAS Model: A Case Study of Y Distillery

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20555460>

Published Date : 05-June-2026

Abstract: This study takes China's Y Distillery as a case, integrates the SICAS model and 4I theory, and uses in-depth interviews to explore its live streaming e-commerce marketing strategies. The research finds that the enterprise faces issues such as passive brand exposure, homogeneous content, single interaction forms, purchase reliance on price promotions, and low sharing willingness. Based on the identified problems, an optimization strategy is proposed: at the perception level, build a short video matrix to enhance proactive reach; at the interest level, use storytelling content to establish emotional resonance; at the connection level, deepen two-way interaction through brewer Q&A sessions; at the action level, develop cultural co-branded gift boxes to drive value-based purchasing; at the sharing level, design a rebate mechanism to activate word-of-mouth viral spread. This study provides theoretical references and practical pathways for optimizing live streaming marketing strategies of traditional old enterprises.

Keywords: SICAS model; 4I theory; live streaming e-commerce; marketing strategy optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In China, with the continuous maturation of mobile internet and the rapid development of science and technology, more and more social media platforms such as Tiktok, Little Red Book, and Kuaishou have emerged. Based on social media platforms and the internet, live streaming has arisen, attracting a large number of online users. With the arrival of the pandemic, people were unable to go out, and a large number of consumers turned to online shopping, making it the main arena for consumer spending. Many enterprises sensed the business opportunity and began to establish their own e-commerce live streaming departments to sell products online, hoping to open new sales channels through online sales. The emergence of e-commerce live streaming has boosted sales and had a positive impact on brand image. Live streaming allows consumers to view product details clearly in the live stream, facilitating and satisfying people's shopping needs.

The current research on live-streaming e-commerce mainly focuses on the factors influencing consumer behavior, the market scale and future development trends, innovations in operational models, and the anchor ecosystem. Taking China's Y Distillery as an example, this study applies the SICAS model to analyze the marketing strategies employed by Y Distillery in the process of live-streaming sales. It also examines the existing problems in live-streaming sales at the current stage and proposes corresponding countermeasures to improve the live-streaming e-commerce marketing strategies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. E-commerce live streaming sales

E-commerce livestreaming refers to a marketing approach that promotes and sells products online through the use of the internet, big data, and various social media platforms. Xu (2021) believes that livestreaming sales leverage the vast traffic network of internet platforms to provide product traceability and multidimensional product introductions to meet customers' shopping expectations. Online sales break through the constraints of time and space, offering greater flexibility and becoming an important marketing method suited to the times ^[1].

Huang and Suo (2021) also argued that during the livestream process, the broadcaster's traits and interactive elements can influence consumers' perception of value, which in turn directly or indirectly affects purchasing behavior^[2]. Wang and Guo (2025) believes that live streaming marketing strategy is a marketing approach where hosts and related personnel use major live streaming platforms to showcase the brand, characteristics, functions, and selling points of products or services through professional scripts, while enhancing the atmosphere to stimulate consumers' willingness to purchase^[3]. Zhou (2023) suggests that products should first increase exposure, then co-create value with users to expand brand influence, integrate online community services with official sales platforms, merge online and offline channels, and ultimately achieve sales conversion^[4]. Zeng (2023) states that in interactive marketing, the focus should be on enhancing exposure and feedback, building trust and encouraging participation, increasing preference and satisfaction, and boosting repeat purchases and word-of-mouth recommendations to achieve effective marketing^[5]. Wan, Chen, Yu et al. (2025) believes that more professional hosts, better live streaming environments, and improved content can make brands more influential^[6]. Liu, Aremu and Yoo, (2020) points out that through celebrity influencers, distinctive content, and short video collaboration, brands can create their own differentiated style to attract targeted audiences^[7]. Ago (2023) proposes using interactive tools such as chatbots and comments in e-commerce live streaming to improve product marketing effectiveness and promote business expansion^[8]. In summary, live streaming marketing strategy is a network-based marketing method that promotes and markets products through media platforms to stimulate consumer interest and achieve marketing goals. The types of live streaming marketing strategies can be categorized into content marketing, interactive marketing, and marketing campaign planning, achieving a shift from broad outreach to precision marketing.

B. .4I Marketing Theory

The 4I theory was proposed by American marketing professor Don Schultz, and its core consists of four basic principles: Interesting, Interests, Interaction, and Individuality, serving as a marketing theory model in the Internet era^[9]. The 4I theory is consumer-centric: first attracting consumers' attention, then guiding and encouraging them to participate actively, allowing them to have a satisfying experience, and ultimately achieving marketing goals step by step. According to Yuyuan, Husain, and Baki (2023), "Interests" refers to the benefits consumers obtain during the marketing process; "Interesting" refers to engaging content that can draw consumers' attention and keep them watching, potentially stimulating purchase behavior; "Individuality" aims to evoke audience resonance, thereby enhancing their purchasing desire and loyalty; "Interaction" refers to strengthening the information exchange between enterprises and consumers and improving marketing effectiveness through interaction^[10]. Junran (2022) believes that "Interesting" is the key factor in attracting consumer attention, while "Interests" emphasizes that marketing activities should bring practical value to consumers. This includes the material level, such as various discounts and rich rewards, as well as the spiritual level, such as making consumers feel satisfied and delighted; "Individuality" requires that marketing activities be custom-designed according to consumer differences; "Interaction" focuses on the characteristics of two-way communication in marketing activities^[11]. Jiao (2025) believes that the 4I theory can meet the needs of multi-faceted analysis in live-stream marketing^[12], helping to identify existing marketing strategy problems and optimize them, so that potential users can be converted into actual consumers.

C. SICAS Model

The SICAS model is a consumer behavior analysis model proposed by the China Internet Network Information Center in 2011, comprising five dimensions: Sense, Interest, Connect, Action, and Share. Weiling and Wongkumchai (2025) believes that the SICAS model is a comprehensive framework for analyzing the evolution of consumer behavior, covering the entire process from the initial stage of consumer perception of the brand, to stimulating interest, interacting with merchants, experiencing purchase, and sharing^[13]. Yigai, Anyi, Huang et al. (2023) suggests that the SICAS model can be used to understand user needs, thereby designing marketing strategies that meet those needs, significantly improving marketing effectiveness and conversion efficiency^[14].

In the traditional media environment, consumers follow the five major stages of the AIDMA model to complete their consumption decisions, whereas the SICAS model, compared to traditional consumer behavior theories, places greater emphasis on the consumer-driven psychology within the social media environment, focusing on the dominant role of user consumption behaviors characterized by instant sharing. Zeng, Liu, Zhang et al. (2023) believes that the SICAS model, through quantitative methods, thoroughly analyzes consumers' full-cycle behaviors in stages such as brand perception, interest stimulation, interaction with sellers, and post-purchase sharing^[15]. Huang (2019) considers that the SICAS model offers a comprehensive, multidimensional approach to understanding consumer behavior, enabling enterprises to more

accurately identify consumer needs and strengthen the connection between various stages of marketing, thereby effectively carrying out live-streaming marketing activities^[16]. Wuisan and Handra (2023) points out that integrating the SICAS model with precision marketing theory can optimize live-streaming marketing strategies^[17].

Overall, the SICAS model is an innovative marketing evaluation model based on the digital era, building upon the previous AIDMA and AISAS models. It is a panoramic, multi-dimensional interactive approach that helps companies in profiling consumers, thereby facilitating the development of better marketing strategies.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Case Introduction

Y Distillery was founded in 1956 and was transformed into a private enterprise in March 2000. As of 2025, the company holds 39 patents, covering utility model technologies such as rice soaking machines and gas filters; it owns 27 trademarks. The plant covers an area of 23,000 square meters, an annual production capacity of 10,000 tons, and its base liquor production capacity has been increased to three times the original level.

B. Interview Analysis

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the existing issues in the brewery's current live-stream marketing, 20 consumers were selected for in-depth interviews. Dworkin (2012) suggested that, in qualitative research using in-depth interviews, a sample size of 5 to 50 is appropriate^[18]. Therefore, this study recruited 20 suitable interviewees, of whom 18 were consumers who had watched the Distillery's live-streams and 2 were marketing personnel from the Distillery.

FIGURE 1: RESEARCH FRAMEWORK DIAGRAM

The interview topics are primarily designed around the five aspects of SICAS, conducting interviews with consumers and corporate marketing personnel to collect users' overall evaluations and suggestions regarding the case. The collected data is organized and summarized through content analysis, with the interview results presented in TABLE 1 to 3

TABLE 1: RESPONDENTS' COGNITION AND INTERESTS STATISTICS

Title	Answer Summary	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Impact on Brand Awareness	Practical	4	14.29
	Truth	4	14.29
	Cultural Heritage	3	10.71
	Brand Impression	3	10.71
	Attitude towards brewing	2	7.14
	Sense of identity	2	7.14

	Demand	2	7.14
	Transparent	2	7.14
	Non-pure promotion	2	7.14
	Quality	2	7.14
	Interest	2	7.14
Interest Stimulation	Craft Demonstration	2	33.33
	Product Story	2	33.33
	Craft Narrative	1	16.67
	Brewing Process	1	16.67

TABLE 2: LIVE STREAMING CONNECTION INTERACCCTION STATISTICS

Title	Answer Summary	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Interactive method	Discount	5	23.81
	Craft	3	14.29
	Lottery	3	14.29
	Texture	2	9.52
	Q&A Activity	2	9.52
	Delivery	2	9.52
	Scene	2	9.52
	Product	2	9.52
Guided interaction and image building	Responses incorporating alcohol-related knowledge	2	50
	Optimize live streaming content based on data	1	25
	Design interactive questions	1	25

TABLE 3: THE REASONS FOR PURCHASE AND SHARE FACTIONS

Title	Answer Summary	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Order Reason	Price	13	31.71
	Packaging Design	8	19.51
	Discount	7	17.07
	Transportation and Delivery	5	12.19
	Gift	4	9.76
	Purchase Process	4	9.76
Recommendation willingness	Willing	8	32
	Good self-purchase experience	3	12
	Cost-effectiveness	3	12
	Content	3	12
	The product is informative	2	8
	Not recommended	2	8
	Price has an advantage	2	8
Product Features	2	8	

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Existing Problems

Based on the literature review and interview results, combined with the current live streaming strategy of the case, the five dimensions of the SICAS model (Perception, Interest, Connection, Action, Sharing) and the 4I theory (Fun, Benefit, Interaction, Individuality), the comprehensive analysis is summarized as follows:

1. Sense — Insufficient brand exposure and content appeal

Brand exposure mainly relies on occasional platform recommendations, lacking proactive communication strategies and strong content appeal, failing to effectively "capture" users. Interview data shows that among preferred content, "brewing process" accounts for only 9.52%, and "historical background" for 7.94%. In staff interviews, brand exposure methods are mainly "background board + logo," lacking diversified content dissemination, indicating the content has not sparked broad interest.

2. Interest Level — Content homogenization, lacking sustained appeal

Although the live-stream content has a certain level of knowledge, it overall lacks entertainment value and emotional resonance, making it difficult to establish long-term user engagement. From the interview data, it can be seen that the proportion of preference for entertaining content such as "bartending tutorials," "stories," and "design sense" is all less than 5%. Company staff mentioned "craftsmanship display" and "product stories" as means to spark interest, but did not mention the design of entertaining content.

3. Connection Level (Connect) — Single form of interaction, lacking deep connection

Interactions mostly remain at the levels of 'Q&A' and 'lottery', lacking emotional connection and value co-creation, and failing to establish a deep relationship between users and the brand. Interview data reveals that consumers focus most on 'discounts' (27.78%) and 'lottery' (16.67%) during interactions, while paying less attention to in-depth content such as 'craftsmanship' and 'taste'. The way company staff guide interactions is mainly through 'integrating liquor knowledge into answers' and 'designing interactive questions', lacking a systematic interaction strategy. Only 50% of consumers expressed that 'both their goodwill and purchase intention have increased', indicating that the interaction has some effect.

4. Action – Purchase conversion relies on price promotions, lacking value-driven incentives

Consumers place orders mainly driven by 'price' and 'discounts', rather than product culture or brand value, making the conversion path fragile. Interview data shows that among the reasons for placing orders, 'price' accounts for 72.22%, 'discounts' for 38.89%, while 'cultural value' accounts for only 5.56%; company staff mainly promote purchases through 'price', 'free gifts' and 'simplified ordering', lacking brand value guidance; although consumers recognize the 'one-click ordering' function, their purchasing decisions still heavily rely on promotions.

5. Sharing Level (Share) — Low willingness to share, lacking motivation for dissemination

Consumers have weak willingness to recommend, and there is a lack of incentive mechanisms for sharing behaviors, making it difficult for the brand to form a closed loop of word-of-mouth communication. Interview data show that the willingness to recommend accounts for 44.44%, but 11.11% clearly stated 'would not recommend'. The main factors influencing recommendations are 'value' (38.89%) and 'responsibility and authenticity' (22.22%), indicating that users are cautious about recommendation behaviors. Company personnel did not mention any strategies regarding 'user sharing incentives' or 'social communication'.

B. Optimization Strategies

Based on the SICAS model and the 4I theory, and drawing from literature and interview data, this paper proposes the following targeted optimization strategies:

1. Sense — Enhance proactive brand exposure and increase content engagement

Build a "short video + livestream" content matrix to enhance the brand's proactive reach. By creating a series of short video content centered on consumer-preferred themes such as "brewing techniques," "historical stories," and "cocktail tutorials," produce engaging 15–30 second videos and distribute them on platforms such as Douyin, Kuaishou, and WeChat Channels to attract active user attention. Leverage AI and VR technologies to enhance immersion, creating immersive experiences by integrating virtual distillery tours and 3D product displays into short videos to increase content appeal.

Launch a 'Distillery Open Day' live streaming preview, regularly release preview announcements, and guide users to book and watch.

2. Interest Level — Enrich content layers and establish emotional resonance

Centering on 'story + experience,' design storytelling content about 'wine and people' to create differentiated live-streaming content. Invite local cultural celebrities and master brewers to share the '70-year history of a winemaking family' to enhance emotional resonance. Launch an interactive 'Mixology Lab' segment with cocktail-making tutorials and creative drinks to increase fun. Establish a 'user-voted live-stream theme' mechanism, allowing fans to vote for the next live-stream topic to enhance user engagement and anticipation.

3. Connection Level (Connect) — Deepen interactive formats and establish a two-way communication mechanism

Invite winemakers to join the live stream every month to answer user questions in real time and enhance professional trust. Start live streaming at key winemaking stages to showcase the transparent production process. Set up a 'You Ask, I Answer' section during the live stream to improve response efficiency.

4. Action — Shift from price-driven to value-driven, optimizing the purchasing experience

Build a 'Value + Trust' conversion path to enhance the quality of purchase decisions. Based on consumers' interest in 'packaging design' and 'exclusive customization services', develop high value-added products such as 'co-branded editions' and 'custom sealed jar liquor'. Embed 'winemaker recommendations', 'authentic user reviews', and 'product traceability information' at the top of the purchase link page to strengthen the value basis for purchase decisions. Optimize the experience loop after 'one-click ordering': once users complete their purchase, automatically push 'short videos on brewing techniques' and 'drinking guides' to continue brand value delivery.

5. Sharing Aspect (Share) — Activate users' motivation to spread, and build a word-of-mouth viral mechanism

Build a sharing mechanism driven by both "content + incentives", inviting consumers to shoot short videos, with outstanding works published on the official account and rewarded. Set up a "share for rewards" viral mechanism, where users can click the "share" button in the livestream to receive "exclusive coupons + lottery eligibility"; after sharing, if friends place an order, they can also receive "sharing commission" or "points rewards". Turn genuine consumer feedback into a "wall of testimonials" to be displayed in rotation during livestreams, enhancing new users' trust.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper takes Y Distillery as a case study, combining literature research, in-depth interviews, and case analysis methods, and applies the SICAS model and 4I theory to explore the distillery's marketing strategies in depth. The study finds that Y Distillery adopts traditional e-commerce marketing strategies in live-stream sales to achieve brand exposure and accumulate user attention, but due to a lack of innovation, it still faces problems such as insufficient brand exposure and content appeal, homogenized content, lack of deep connection with users, conversion rate lacking value-driven factors, and low willingness for user sharing. In response to these issues, this paper proposes improvement strategies including enhancing brand exposure through entertaining content, strengthening content depth with "content + experience," establishing mechanisms to deepen interaction, increasing value-driven conversion, and achieving word-of-mouth viral growth via users. These strategies aim to precisely address the marketing strategy problems in the case study, help the distillery break through the traditional old-brand dilemma of "good reputation but no traffic," and rejuvenate the brand's vitality.

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